

FABRICATION AND PERFORMANCE OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH HYBRID OF NANOCCLAY AND MWCNTs

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ABSTRACT

Fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites show significantly superior performance over many traditional metallic materials because of their superior strength to weight ratio and higher stiffness. Significant development in the use of nanoparticles for modification of epoxy matrix has led to improved mechanical properties of the FRP composites. Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites were modified with 2 wt. % Montmorillonite nanoclay and 0.3 wt. % multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). A hybrid system wherein 2 wt. % of nanoclay and 0.1 wt. % of MWCNTs was also developed. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), Thermo-Mechanical Analysis (TMA), and 3-point bending tests were conducted for characterizing samples. Low Velocity Impact (LVI) tests were conducted at different energy levels. Impact damage was characterized through thermography. Results obtained from these experiments were compared with unmodified carbon/epoxy composites. Reinforcement with nanoparticles was found to significantly improve the mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties of composites. Addition of nanoparticles in composites caused significant improvement in mechanical and viscoelastic properties compared to those of control ones. Best results were obtained for addition of 0.1% MWCNT/2% MMT hybrid nanoparticles in epoxy. Composites modified with hybrid nanoparticles exhibited about 15% increase in storage modulus as well as 10° C increase in glass transition temperature. Flexural modulus for hybrid nanoparticle modified composites depicted about 30% improvement compared to control ones. Viscoelastic properties like storage and loss modulus increased by over 40% and coefficient of thermal expansion decreased both in the inplane and through the thickness directions. Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites modified with MMT/MWCNTs hybrid nanoparticles displayed better impact resistance than control samples. Improved impact resistance of modified composites will help to address some of the major issues with using composite materials in naval vessels and offshore structures without sacrificing the advantages of composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of polymer composite materials in civil/offshore structures and US naval and military applications has been increasing steadily in the last several years [1]. Fiber reinforced polymer composites show significantly superior performance over many traditional metallic materials because of their superior strength and stiffness to weight ratios which translate into higher acceleration, manoeuvrability, and fuel efficiency. Polyester or vinylester resins and glass fiber have been widely used for manufacturing of commodity vehicles. However, carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites are preferred for designing performance driven vehicles like speed boats [2]. Mechanical properties of fiber reinforced polymer composites depend on the fiber, matrix and the interface between them. As the properties of the matrix significantly influences the performance of the composite structure, enhancement of properties of FRP composites can be possible by the modification of matrix properties. Significant development in the use of nanoparticles for modification of epoxy matrix has led to improved mechanical properties of the FRP composites. To improve the properties of both thermoset and thermoplastic composites, researchers have been using nanoparticles. The advantages of

nanoparticles are their high specific strength and modulus, low density along with large surface area available for chemical interactions. Moreover, addition of very low percentage of nanoparticles can enhance the properties of composites significantly. Various organic and inorganic nanoparticles are used as reinforcement of composites. Among them, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are the strongest materials known [3], however they are expensive, hazardous and have high length to diameter ratio. Less expensive organic materials like nanoclays are also popular for composite reinforcement. Nanoclays are layered structures capable of reinforcing the matrix to enhance mechanical properties. They act as moisture barriers to provide environmental degradation resistance [4]. Recently, reinforcing composites with two nanoparticles together is becoming popular. Sometimes, two or more nanoparticles are synthesized together and applied as reinforcement to composites. Then they are called hybrid nanoparticles [5]. Sometimes two nanoparticles are used as reinforcement despite being synthesized separately. Generally, nanoparticles employed together possess different physical and chemical properties to be compatible together.

Impact damage resistance is one of the main concerns of fiber reinforced composite structure due to its poor trans-laminar properties. MWCNTs have been found to improve the low velocity impact resistance of FRP composites [6, 7]. Besides, researchers have observed that incorporation of nanoclays in an epoxy matrix reduced the impact damage size [8]. Hossain et al. [9] compared the low velocity impact response of nanoclay modified carbon/epoxy composites and observed that nanophased composites retained better properties after submersion in seawater. Previous researches conducted in our lab have found that addition of 0.3 wt. % of MWCNTs results in the greatest improvement of mechanical properties [10]. On the other hand, addition of 2 wt. % of nanoclays exhibited best mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties [11]. Incorporation of additional amount of nanoparticles led to decrease in properties due to agglomeration. To further enhance the properties of nano-reinforced composites, addition of two different kinds of nanoparticles in epoxy matrix can be explored. Addition of MWCNTs along with nanoclays has been studied by various researchers and was found to have a synergistic effect on improving the thermal properties [12, 13] and electrical properties [14, 15] of polymer composites. Hazarika et al. [16] observed an improvement in elastic modulus, loss modulus and damping index in Wood Polymer Composites by addition of MWCNTs and nanoclays hybrid nanoparticles. However, addition of these two nanoparticles together for improvement of mechanical properties has not been studied much. Also, no studies have been conducted on addition of slight amount of MWCNTs along with nanoclay for improvement of low velocity impact properties of carbon/epoxy composites. In this study, effect of modification of carbon/epoxy composites by adding 0.1 wt. % of COOH functionalized MWCNTs along with 2 wt. % of octadecylamine functionalized MMT nanoclays was investigated. Mechanical, thermal and viscoelastic properties of fiber reinforced composites were investigated by conducting flexure test, dynamic mechanical analysis, thermomechanical analysis and morphological investigation. In addition, low-velocity impact performance was also evaluated. Properties obtained from hybrid nanoparticles reinforced FRP samples were compared with single nanoparticle reinforced FRP and control FRP samples.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Materials

SC-15 Epoxy, a commercially available two part resin system obtained from Applied Poleramic Inc. was used in this research. It is a toughened, low viscosity (300 cps) resin having low shrinkage properties upon curing. This is a room temperature curing resin having pot life of 6 hours, which can also be cured at high temperature. Carbon fiber used in this study was of 8 harness satin weave purchased from US composites. Areal density of the carbon fiber was 0.37 kg/m^2 , tow size 3k and thickness 0.46 mm. Carboxyl functionalized MWCNTs having diameter of 10-20nm and length 10-30 μm were obtained from Nanostructured and Amorphous Materials Inc. Nanomer I-30E, nanoclay that is surface modified with 25-30 wt. % octadecylamine was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Typically, nanoclay contains less than 3% of moisture with a mineral purity of 98.5%. Nanoclays are hydrophilic platelets, which are commercially available with different surface modifications to make them chemically compatible with hydrophobic resins.

2.2 Fabrication of composites

Fabrication process included four different types of samples: Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites (CFRPs) that serve as control laminates, MWCNT modified CFRPs, nanoclay infused CFRPs as well as 0.1 wt. % MWCNT/ 2wt. % nanoclay hybrid nanoparticles reinforced CFRPs. Various dispersion techniques were applied to break up the agglomeration and ensure proper dispersion of nanoparticles in the resin. Different techniques were used to disperse various nanoparticles in resin. In our study, MWCNTs were dispersed using ultra-sonication and three-roll mixing technique. Desired amount of carboxyl functionalized MWCNT was weighed and mixed with calculated amount of epoxy part A manually. Then the mixture was ultra-sonicated at a temperature of 40° C for 30 minutes at 39% amplitude and 30 second on /20 second off pulsating cycle. To facilitate the dispersion and minimize the agglomeration, a three-roll mill was used as a high speed shear mixer. Maximum speed of 150 rpm was maintained while passing the mixture of resin and MWCNTs three times between the rollers. Gap between successive rollers was maintained the same during each pass. Setting of the same was 20 µm for first pass, 10 µm for second pass and 5 µm for the final pass. In case of nanoclays, to drive off the moisture and obtain entirely dry nanoclays, they are placed in vacuum at a temperature 50° C overnight. To disperse nanoclays, sonication and magnetic stirring were used. At first, calculated amount of nanoclay was weighed and mixed with resin manually and ultra-sonicated using same conditions as in the case of nanotubes. Then the mixture was magnetically stirred at 800 rpm for 24 hours at a temperature 50° C. In order to disperse MWCNTs and nanoclay together combination of various methods was applied and uniform dispersion was achieved through a complex and prolonged procedure based on our prior studies. In this process, MWCNTs were mixed with epoxy through ultra-sonication for 20 minutes at 39% amplitude and 30 second on/20 second off pulse cycle to ensure uniform dispersion. Then nanoclays were added and the mixture was ultrasonicated again for 15 minutes using same conditions. After that, the mixture was stirred magnetically at 800 rpm for 24 hours at a temperature 50°C. Finally, three-roll shear mixer was used to ensure consistent and uniform dispersion of hybrid nano-particles in the epoxy resin. After dispersion, part A of SC-15 epoxy containing nanoparticles was mixed with part B at a ratio 10:3. High speed mechanical mixing was done for 10 minutes to obtain a stoichiometric mixture, which was then utilized as matrix for laminates. For control samples, only Part A and part B of SC-15 resin were mixed at a stoichiometric ratio and used as matrix. The resin mixture was degasified at 60° C. Carbon fiber-epoxy nanocomposites were fabricated by a combination of hand lay-up process and compression molding technique. A total of eight layers of woven carbon fabrics were used. For curing, temperature was kept at 60° C for 1 hour to attain enough flow of resin at lower viscosity as compared to room temperature and at the same time not to let it flow out of the layup. Temperature was then increased to 120° C and maintained for 3 hours to obtain completely cured carbon-epoxy composites. Thickness of laminates obtained was about 2.42 mm.

2.3 Characterization Techniques

Fiber reinforced composites were subjected to various tests to obtain the mechanical, thermal and viscoelastic properties. Properties obtained from nanoparticles modified composites were compared with the properties obtained from control ones. Moreover microscopic and morphological analyses were performed on fracture surface of the samples.

Flexure test

In our research, flexure test was conducted according to ASTM D790-02. The test was conducted in three-point bending configuration using Zwick-Reoll Z 2.5 machine. The test was performed at a rate 1.2 mm/minute under displacement control mode. The sample size was maintained according to the ASTM, where span length to thickness ratio is 16:1. The sample size was 60 mm × 12.5 mm × 2.5 mm.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

Viscoelastic properties of both nanocomposites and fiber reinforced composites are obtained from dynamic mechanical analysis. DMA tests were conducted according to ASTM D4065-12 using TA

instrument DMA Q 800. The tests were performed in three point bending mode at a frequency 1 Hz and amplitude 15 μm . The temperature ramp was 10° C/minute within the range 30° C and 180° C. The sample size was 60 mm \times 13 mm \times 3 mm for the test.

Thermo mechanical analysis (TMA)

Thermo-mechanical analysis was conducted to obtain the coefficient of thermal expansion from samples. The test was done according to ASTM D696-03. For fiber reinforced composites, the test was conducted in the inplane and through thickness directions. TA instrument Q 400 was used to conduct the test in expansion mode. The temperature ramp was 10° C/minute within the range 30° C and 180° C. The system is purged by liquid nitrogen gas at a flow rate of 50 ml/minute. Dimension change versus temperature curve was obtained from the test and plotted from which coefficient of linear expansion was determined.

Low Velocity Impact Testing

Low velocity impact tests were conducted using DYNATUP 8210 drop weight impact testing machine. During the test, sample was held with a round edged pneumatically operated clamp fixture. The height and weight of impactor was changed to strike the samples at energy levels of 30J and 40J. As the height of the impactor has to be controlled manually, the impact energy was deviated a little from the desired value every time the experiment was conducted. The machine also records velocity, deflection energy and load as functions of time. Peak load, time to attain the peak load and deflection of samples at peak load were observed from the data acquired and compared for different samples. Other related parameters like absorbed energy were calculated from area under the load versus deflection curve. The samples were also subjected to sea-water conditioning for six months. Impact tests were carried out before and after conditioning to see the effect of nanoparticles in reducing the sea-water environmental effects.

Thermography analysis

A cutting edge thermal imaging instrument was used to qualify and the ensuing damages in the samples. The system consists of a bright flashlight which flashes for a fraction of a second and as a result enables the sample under observation to absorb heat energy. The heat is conducted through and radiated from the surface of the sample. An infrared camera catches up the radiated heat signature of the specimen. The heat conducted or radiated depends on the quality of the sample. This directly provides information on the defects or damages present in any sample. The heat signature comprises of noise. Hence filtration is necessary to clearly observe actual damage in the samples. In our work, the thermal signal was captured for 15 seconds at 30 fps. Then the output signature was differentiated twice to get a noise free signal. The image of the precise moment when the heat signal achieved maximum amplitude was taken into consideration to obtain a color exposure of the surface. The colored image was then converted to a black and white image which clearly differentiates the damaged and undamaged portions. Finally, damage area was calculated using MATLAB coding from this image by taking percentage of black portion of the image as function of the total area.

Scanning electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopic analyses were performed to analyze the fracture mode at higher magnification. Analysis of fracture surfaces was carried out using a JEOL JSM-6400 scanning electron microscope (SEM) at 15 kV accelerating voltage. Specimen surfaces were coated with a thin gold film for SEM observation. One sample from each set impacted at 30 J was observed under scanning electron microscopy to understand failure behavior at various magnifications.

3 RESULTS

In this research, carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites were modified with MWCNTs, nanoclays and hybrid nanoparticles. All types of carbon fiber/epoxy were subjected to flexure,

dynamic mechanical analysis, thermomechanical analysis, morphological and microscopic analysis to obtain mechanical, viscoelastic and thermal properties. Most of the properties such as flexure and DMA were measured through thickness direction. TMA tests were conducted in the plane of laminate and through its thickness. Data from these tests were accumulated and various properties were calculated. Properties obtained for nanoparticles modified carbon fiber/epoxy composites were compared with those of control carbon fiber/epoxy composites.

3.1 Flexure test

Carbon fiber reinforced composites modified with nanoparticles were subjected to three point bending load to compare the flexural properties of nanoparticles modified samples to control. Flexural stress versus strain plots are depicted in figure 1. Figure 1 reveals the influence of nanoparticles on the flexural properties of composites. The comparison of flexural properties among the nanophased and control composites is depicted in figure 2. Flexural strength and modulus of all the samples increased with addition of nanoparticles. The maximum enhancement was observed for hybrid nanoparticles modified CFRPs with an increase of 31% and 30% of flexural strength and modulus.

Figure 1: Flexural Stress versus strain response of control and nanoparticles reinforced carbon fiber/epoxy composite samples.

Figure 2: Comparison of flexural strength and modulus exhibited by nanoparticles reinforced and control carbon fiber/epoxy composite samples.

In fiber reinforced composites, carbon fibers are the primary load carrying agents. Nanoparticles undergo chemical reactions with polymers as well as the functional groups present on the surface of fibers thereby form a very strong chemical bond at the fiber-matrix interface as well as between the layers. In bending load, the composite structure is loaded in thickness direction, in which direction the composite structures are most vulnerable. Individual plies in the composite structure are prone to

separation due to shear stress on the laminate. Hence nanoparticles come into play acting as crack arrestors or bridges between the plies whenever there is an initial of crack which tries to propagate. Thus, when loaded these bridge structures between plies must be severed before delamination, which required more energy to break the specimen. Therefore, nanoparticles are more effective when used as a reinforcement of CFRPs as they reinforce the resin as well as act as bridge structure between individual plies. These were confirmed through SEM studies which are outlined in a later section.

Figure 3: Storage modulus of nanoparticles reinforced and control fiber reinforced composites.

Figure 4: Loss modulus of nanoparticles and control fiber reinforced composites.

3.2 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

Nanophased and control carbon fiber/epoxy composites were subjected to dynamic mechanical analysis to obtain viscoelastic properties. Transient data obtained from this experiment were accumulated and storage moduli, loss moduli and tan-delta as a function of temperature were plotted in as shown in figures 3-5. Storage modulus of all samples as a function of temperature is depicted in figure 3. From figure 3, it is evident that hybrid nanoparticles reinforced carbon fiber/epoxy composites possess much higher storage modulus and glass transition temperature than control composites. Moreover, nanoclays reinforced composites had higher storage modulus, yet lower glass transition temperature. On the contrary, MWCNTs reinforced composites exhibited lower storage modulus, yet high glass transition temperature. Therefore, in hybrid nanoparticles reinforced composites, MWCNTs tend to increase the glass transition temperature along with nanoclays reinforcing the resin mechanically. Loss moduli of control and nanophased carbon fiber/epoxy composites are presented in Figure 4. Loss modulus for nanoparticles reinforced carbon fiber/epoxy composites is much higher than the control composites. Hybrid nanoparticles possess highest loss modulus, thus highest amount of energy is dissipated while three point bending load is applied. When the load is applied, the nanoparticles try to hold the laminae in place, so more amount of energy is

required to deform the samples. Thus, nanoparticles reinforced composites required higher load and loss modulus increased for nanophased composites. Peak values of tan-delta versus temperature plot indicate the damping properties of the composites. Damping properties of nanophased composites are much higher than control composites. Hybrid nanoparticles increase damping properties of carbon fiber/epoxy composites by about 29%. Also glass transition temperature obtained from tan-delta plot exhibits similar behavior as nanocomposites. Nanoclays, MWCNTs and hybrid nanoparticles increase the glass transition temperature by about 12%, 8% and 19% respectively as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Glass transition temperatures obtained from tan-delta plot of carbon fiber /epoxy composites.

3.3 Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA)

Thermo-mechanical analysis of control and nanoparticles reinforced carbon fiber/epoxy composites reveals distinct behavior while performed in different direction. Coefficient of thermal expansion for carbon fiber is negative, thus carbon fiber contracts when temperature increases. On the contrary, epoxy SC-15 resin has a positive CTE. Therefore, carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites were subjected to thermomechanical analysis in both directions: along fiber axis and through thickness direction. Values of coefficient of thermal expansion were calculated from the dimension changes versus temperature plot obtained by testing samples in both directions. Plots of dimension change versus temperature through thickness direction were similar to the plots obtained for TMA of nanocomposites. Thus, CTE values were obtained from the slope of the plots before and after glass transition temperature. Glass transition temperature was obtained from nadir of the plots. CTE values and glass transition temperature for nanophased and control composites through thickness direction are depicted in table 1. It is evident that, the CTE of hybrid nanoparticles are lowest among all samples before and after glass transition temperature. When CTE is measured through thickness direction, it depends on resin. Thus, in control composites when temperature increases, resin starts to transform into rubbery state from a glassy one and each lamina becomes separated. On the contrary, for nanoparticles modified carbon fiber reinforced composites, nanoparticles reinforce the matrix structure and act as bridging structures to laminates. Thus, nanoparticles reinforced carbon fiber/epoxy composites expand less than control composites. For hybrid nanoparticles, nanoclays reinforce the resin being exfoliated in them whereas MWCNTs act as bridging structure between laminae.

Sample Type	CTE before T_g , $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$	% change	CTE after T_g , $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$	% change	T_g , $^{\circ}\text{C}$	% change
Control	81.38±5.28	-	192.78±7.61	-	89.33±0.67	-
Nanoclay reinforced	65.78±4.67	20	141.07±9.49	26	95.13±0.88	7
MWCNT reinforced	64.71±15.42	21	126.89±33.86	34	100.67±1.21	13
Hybrid nanoparticle	57.3±3.18	30	108.2±4.71	44	110.42±0.45	24

Table 1: TMA results for carbon fiber/epoxy composites through thickness.

When tested along the fiber direction, slope of dimension change versus temperature is negative. Thus, CTE values for composites become negative before and after glass transition temperature. Moreover, the CTE values are very near to zero. CTE values for fibers are negative and trifle compared to resin. Along fiber direction, CTE values are very similar to fiber CTE as shown in table 2. For nanoparticles reinforced composites, no significant change in CTE was exhibited as nanoparticles generally influence resin control properties. Therefore, hybrid nanoparticles reinforcement significantly improved CTE through thickness, whereas, no substantial influence was observed on CTE along fiber axis.

Sample Type	CTE before T_g , $10^{-6}/^{\circ}C$	CTE after T_g , $10^{-6}/^{\circ}C$	T_g , $^{\circ}C$
Control	-1.82 ± 2.58	-4.66 ± 1.73	97.34 ± 7.45
Nanoclay reinforced	-2.34 ± 2.57	-2.08 ± 1.46	105.89 ± 4.66
MWCNT reinforced	-3.96 ± 8.069	-3.58 ± 2.77	105.01 ± 1.51
Hybrid nanoparticle	-0.062 ± 0.077	-2.58 ± 2.21	108.61 ± 1.87

Table 2: TMA results for carbon fiber/epoxy composites along fiber direction.

Figure 6: SEM images of fracture surface of fiber reinforced composites at X1000 zoom level (a) control, (b) with nanoclays, (c) with MWCNT and (d) with hybrid nanoparticles.

3.4 Morphological analysis

Fractured surface of different specimen was analyzed through scanning electron microscope. The surface was sputtered with gold and placed under electron beam at 15kV. At first, fracture surface of all the specimens was observed at 1000x magnification level. Figure 6 depicts the images obtained for nanophased and control carbon fiber/epoxy composite on delaminated fracture surface of tensile samples. Nanophased and control samples in both case resembled similar appearance. In case of control samples in figure 6(a), fibers from the fractured surface were completely pulled out for the matrix and the fibers were completely separated as well as severe matrix cracking took place.

On the contrary, microscopic images for MWCNT and hybrid nanoparticles modified composite samples shown partial pull out of fibers from the matrix. Although some of the fibers were separated completely, most of the fibers were attached with others which might be attributed to additional delamination mechanism presented by MWCNTs in nanophased samples. Nanotubes, dispersed in resin act as a bridging structures between the laminae. Hence, at the time of delamination initiation, the bondings between resin and nanotubes as well as bonding between resin and carbon fibers have to be severed. This incident results in absorbing more energy than the control laminates as well as arresting the development of cracks due to fracture and damaging mechanism. On the other hand, nanoclays are layered structures, when dispersed and exfoliated in resin; serve as reinforcement to the resin. Thus, it might check the progress of matrix cracking to reduce the damage in the composite structures. Now, hybrid nanoparticles modified samples have both MWCNTs and nanoclays as reinforcement. Hence, MWCNT might act as a bridge structure between the laminae and nanoclays reinforced the matrix materials thereby diminishing delamination as well as matrix cracking of the samples.

Figure 7: Load vs Displacement response of control and modified carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites at (a) 30J energy level before conditioning (b) 40J energy level before conditioning (c) 30J energy level after conditioning (d) 40J energy level after conditioning.

3.5 Low-Velocity Impact

Low velocity impact test was conducted for control and modified samples at dry condition and after 6 months of sea water conditioning. The tests were conducted at 30J and 40J energy levels. For each energy level three samples of each kind of composites were tested and average of the three measurements is reported. Load vs displacement curves were plotted (figure 7) for all kinds of samples before and after degradation tested at different energy levels. It was found that before conditioning, the modified samples exhibited better performance than control samples at both energy levels. At 30J energy level the load-displacement profile was very smooth for both samples except for a small drop in load and change of the slope in load-displacement curve indicating no catastrophic failure. On the contrary, tests conducted at 40J energy levels shows sudden drop of the profile for both control and modified samples. The sudden drop in load indicates partial or full penetration of the sample. After 6 months of conditioning, at 30J energy level binary nanoparticle modified samples still retained a similar profile as that of the unconditioned sample. However, control samples exhibited substantial drop of load after reaching the peak. This sudden drop signifies that control samples were degraded by absorption of moisture after submerging in marine environmental conditions. Tests conducted at 40J energy level also confirm this observation by displaying reduced peak load and lower time for maximum load. Modified samples also showed slight degradation due to moisture absorption. However, the degradation for nanoparticle modified samples was considerably lower compared to control samples signifying increased durability. Octa-decylamine functionalization of MMT may have bonded with COOH functionalization of MWCNTs. As a result more energy was required to break this bond and damage the modified samples which give the binary nanoparticle modified samples significant advantage over control samples.

Figure 4: Thermography images of different samples before and after conditioning at 30J and 40J energy levels.

3.6 Thermography Analysis

Thermal images of the samples after low velocity impact tests were taken and the damage area was measured. The images are illustrated through figure 8. Calculated damage areas of the samples are compared and are listed in table 3. Significant reduction of damage area for binary nanoparticles modified samples was observed before and after conditioning. Moreover, this reduction was found to increase after conditioning which indicates increased durability of the modified carbon/epoxy samples. The reduction of damage area is more significant at 30J energy level.

Conditioning	Damage	30J		40J	
		Control carbon/epoxy	Modified carbon/epoxy	Control carbon/epoxy	Modified carbon/epoxy
None	Area	38.47	15.79	101.55	59.66
	% reduction	-	58.96	-	41.25
6 Months	Area	124.09	43.73	186.24	89.60
	% reduction	-	64.76	-	51.89

Table 3: Calculated damage area of different samples before and after conditioning.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Nanoparticles reinforcement enhances almost all the properties of CFRPs evaluated from tests conducted. Binary nanoparticles exhibited best properties among the nanoparticles reinforced composites:

- Flexural strength and modulus increased by about 30% and 31% respectively for binary nanoparticles reinforced nanocomposites.
- Binary nanoparticles reinforced nanocomposites exhibited about 40%, 44% and 19% improvement in storage modulus, loss modulus and glass transition temperature.
- Coefficient of thermal expansion differs substantially when measured along fiber axis and through thickness direction.
- Coefficient of thermal expansion decreases about 30% and 44% respectively for binary nanoparticles incorporation before and after glass transition temperature when measured through thickness. Along fiber direction nanoparticles incorporation does not influence the CTE significantly.
- Morphological analysis exhibit higher interfacial adhesion of resin and fibers for nanoparticles incorporation. For binary nanoparticles, interfacial adhesion results in much more load carrying capability for composites compared to other nanophased or control composites.
- Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites modified with MMT/MWCNTs binary nanoparticles displayed better impact resistance than control samples.
- This retention of properties signifies that modification with MMT nanoclays along with MWCNTs slowed marine environmental degradation of carbon/epoxy composites and increased durability. The improvement is more pronounced at lower impact energy level.

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